

Supplementary Materials

Table S1. Subgroup analysis in patients with medical emergency team activation due to respiratory causes

Variables	Overall (N=3,854)		Repeat MET activation		<i>p</i>		
			Yes (n=606)	No (n=3,248)			
Age, yr	65	(54-74)	65	(52-73)	65	(54-74)	0.201
Male gender, n (%)	2523	(65.5)	403	(66.5)	2120	(65.3)	0.577
Department							
Medicine	3289	(85.3)	558	(92.1)	2731	(84.1)	<0.001
Surgery	565	(14.7)	48	(7.9)	517	(15.9)	
Comorbidities, n (%)							
Solid tumor	1779	(46.2)	184	(30.4)	1595	(49.1)	<0.001
Hematological malignancies	517	(13.4)	149	(24.6)	368	(11.3)	<0.001
Chronic lung disease	696	(18.1)	130	(21.5)	566	(17.4)	<0.011
Chronic heart disease	1741	(45.2)	279	(46.0)	1462	(45.0)	0.336
Chronic liver disease	434	(11.3)	57	(9.4)	377	(11.6)	0.064
Chronic renal disease	190	(4.9)	31	(5.1)	159	(4.9)	0.441
Vital parameter at first MET activation							
SBP (mmHg)	125	(108-144)	123	(105-140)	125	(109-145)	<0.001
HR (beats/min)	110	(94-126)	110	(94-128)	110	(93-126)	0.805
RR (breaths/min)	27	(22-32)	27	(22-32)	27	(22-32)	0.076
BT (°C)	36.8	(36.5-37.5)	36.9	(36.5-37.6)	36.8	(36.5-37.5)	0.111
SpO ₂ (%)	93	(89-97)	94	(90-97)	93	(88-97)	<0.001
FiO ₂ (%)	0.45	(0.29-0.60)	0.50	(0.37-0.60)	0.45	(0.29-0.53)	<0.001
SpO ₂ /FiO ₂ ratio	202	(157-303)	186	(156-248)	209	(159-324)	<0.001
MEWS	5	(3-6)	5	(3-7)	5	(3-6)	0.016
SOFA	5	(3-7)	6	(4-9)	5	(3-8)	<0.001

MET=medical emergency team, SBP=systolic blood pressure, HR=heart rate, RR=respiratory rate, BT=body temperature, MEWS=modified early warning score, SOFA=sequential organ failure assessment.

Data are expressed as median with interquartile range or number (percentage)